

Stainless Shipping Container

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Abstract. In Human History, regarding the development of the human world, the need to carry stuff became more than before. Human power used to be used, and after a while, animal power was used for carrying commodities. After the development of technology, cargo was delivered by vehicles. Before containerization known as “Container Revolution”, goods were usually handled manually as break-bulk cargo. Goods would be loaded onto a vehicle from the factory carried to Warehouses, and finally loaded on the vessel as bulk cargo. In this type, many parts of goods would be demolished or stolen. After World War II, 1955 former trucking company owner Malcolm McLean worked with engineer Keith Tantlinger to develop the modern intermodal container. Their idea was to remove a part of the truck, seal that, and loading on the vessel to carry that. Nowadays more than a million containers have been made for carrying goods. They are made from iron. And some factories are using weaker alloys to reduce costs. But the thing is even with using different alloys, Metal Oxidation occurs at a huge price for their owners and after a while they become useless. Also, they are strong less, so damages occur at a huge cost for the vendors of Shipping companies. Some solutions are provided such as using Stainless alloy, but it costs too much and also it is so heavy; that the Shipping owners cannot carry so much cargo. According to our research, we found some alloys that can be light, strong, and stainless.

Keywords: Stainless Alloy . Shipping Container . Logistic . Malcom Mclean . Iron-aluminum-molybdenum-alloy . Chromium-free

1 Introduction

Humans used to use animals’ power to solve their solution about carrying cargo which needed more power than human power. After the development of technology, Vehicles, Cargo vessels, and cargo aircraft have been made. But the Logical and cheapest way is using the Vessel. Because around $\frac{3}{4}$ of Earth contains water, and according to Archimedes law that known as Buoyancy [1], we can carry a huge volume of heavy goods as same as swimming animals on water [1] in the cheapest choice. We used to use the Bulk cargo transition type. But many parts of commodities were supposed to be lost, stolen, or even demolished. After WWII, Malcolm McLean and Keith Tantlinger decided to make a box that could be sealed. Their idea was to remove a part of the truck, seal that, and load it on the vessel to keep the cargo from any humidity, water, or even sun destructors. Also, because they seal no part of the cargo would be lost and nobody can steal the cargo. The manufacturers were used to

build the containers with Iron. They were heavy and strong, but nowadays container factories are using a weaker alloy to reduce the Tare Weight of the container for carrying more cargo and reduce the building cost, unfortunately, the Quality is reduced too and the damages have become more than before. Also, all containers would have metal Oxidation. In a shipping container, strong, cheap, light, and stainless parameters determine its quality. A solution that we provided for it is using Iron-Base Alloys Strengthened for Stainless Steels[2] to make the containers stronger. Also, Iron-aluminum-molybdenum-alloy as a Chromium-free Stainless-Steel Substitute[3] can be used for the container alloy to make containers stronger, lighter, and stainless.

2 Shipping Container

After World War II Malcolm McLean presented the idea of splitting a part of a truck for the load on the vessel to keep the cargo safe and in good condition. Figure 1 and Figure 2 are exploded views of a shipping container and would describe the different parts of that. They are in many different types and sizes. Shipping containers are made in different sizes but the most popular sizes of containers are 20 Feet and 40 Feet. 20 Feet containers also known as TEU. Also, factories provided different types such as Open Top, Flat Rack, and Reefer Containers for special commodities.

Fig. 2.

All of the container's body except the floor is made from metals. So, it is so important to use a good alloy to make containers stronger, lighter, and stainless.

3 Iron-Base Alloys Strengthened for Stainless Steels

Studies of the ternary Fe-Mo-Ti system indicate small additions of titanium can be combined with molybdenum additions of less than 8-wt- pct to produce hardening characteristics of good magnitude and resistance to over-aging typical of the binary iron-molybdenum system.[4]

According to Gardner, L. research[4], below contents are conspicuous:

1. The stability of the hardening response in binary iron-molybdenum can be combined with the high magnitude of hardening of the binary iron-titanium system to yield a ternary alloy that has useful hardening characteristics and a broad composition range.

Aluminum and chromium additions have marked effects on solid solubility limits in the ternary Fe - Mo - Ti system

2. Aluminum additions increase the range of solid solubility of molybdenum and titanium in ferritic iron. The vol -pct of precipitation in solution-treated and aged material is decreased by the presence of aluminum, and the size of precipitates solution-treated and aged material is increased.

3. Chromium decreased the range of solid solubility of molybdenum and titanium in ferritic iron. The vol - pct of precipitates in solution-treated and aged alloys is increased by the presence of chromium, and at least two separate intermetallic precipitates containing chromium were observed. Chromium induces a fine precipitate in solution-treated and aged alloys.

4. For optimum stress-rupture properties, precipitate size and distribution, solid solution strengthening, and the magnitude of precipitation hardening response are all factors to be considered. Stress-rupture properties equivalent to 304 and 316 stainless steels can be achieved.

5. Based on workability, hardening characteristics, mechanical properties, and oxidation studies, a composition range of Fe-4 to 6 pct Mo - 2 to 3 pct Ti - 2 to 4 pct Al and 3 to 8 pct Cr were selected for optimization and characterization studies

4 Iron-aluminum-molybdenum-alloy as a Chromium-free Stainless-Steel Substitute

The major conclusions are drawn from the study of Dunning, J. S researches of the ferritic Fe -Al -Mo alloy series in the Bureau of Mines Department of the Interior of the United States of America are outlined below.

1. The alloy responded well to scaled-up melting practice. No major problems were encountered with either vacuum induction melting or air induction melting under an argon shield.

2. The alloy was readily workable in the 700° to 1,050° C temperature range.

3. Columbium and cerium additions had little effect on mechanical properties, oxidation resistance, or carbide precipitation.

4. Fine dispersions of ZrC precipitates could not be reproduced. Carbide precipitation occurs from the liquid phase (melt), and resolution and reprecipitation were not feasible.

5. The 8-wt-pct-Al alloy had excellent oxidation resistance at 700° C. Carbide dispersions were not detrimental to oxidation resistance.

6. The ZrC precipitates were not effective in improving the elevated temperature strength of the alloy. more reliable carbide strengthening mechanism must be developed if the high-temperature strengths of 304 and 316 stainless steel are to be attained. Basic studies of ZrC precipitation together with a survey of other carbide-strengthening mechanisms are recommended.

5 Conclusion

Ocean Shipping is the economically best way to carry cargo. So, it is logical to use too many Shipping Containers around the world. Nowadays many Shipping containers are used in the shipping process. The problems of shipping containers e.g., Oxidation and damage reviewed. Using too many metals in this way is a waste of access to this God-given blessing and can waste our resources. Also, it is not economical for owners of containers and folks. So, two ways to increase the quality of the alloy and make it stainless are provided based on reviewing the Bureau of Mines Department of the Interior of the United States of America.

References

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